

TECHNICAL ADVANCE

An improved extraction method enables the comprehensive analysis of lipids, proteins, metabolites and phytohormones from a single sample of leaf tissue under water-deficit stress

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SUMMARY

Phytohormones play essential roles in the regulation of growth and development in plants. Plant hormone profiling is therefore essential to understand developmental processes and the adaptation of plants to biotic and/or abiotic stresses. Interestingly, commonly used hormone extraction and profiling methods do not adequately resolve other molecular entities, such as polar metabolites, lipids, starch and proteins, which would be required to comprehensively describe the continuing biological processes at a systematic level. In this article we introduce an updated version of a previously published liquid:liquid metabolite extraction protocol, which not only allows for the profiling of primary and secondary metabolites, lipids, starch and proteins, but also enables the quantitative analysis of the major plant hormone classes, including abscisic acid, auxins, cytokinins, jasmonates and salicylates, from a single sample aliquot. The optimization of the method, which uses the introduction of acidified water, enabling the complete purification of major plant hormones into the organic (methyl-*tert*-butyl-ether) phase, eliminated the need for solid-phase extraction for sample clean-up, and therefore reduces both sampling time and cost. As a proof-of-concept analysis, *Arabidopsis thaliana* plants were subjected to water-deficit stress, which were then profiled for hormonal, metabolic, lipidomic and proteomic changes. Surprisingly, we determined not only previously described molecular changes but also significant changes regarding the breakdown of specific galactolipids, followed by the substantial accumulation of unsaturated fatty-acid derivatives and diverse jasmonates in the course of adaptation to water-deficit stress.

Keywords: phytohormones, metabolite extraction, *Arabidopsis thaliana*, omics, water-deficit stress.

INTRODUCTION

Plant hormones, commonly described as phytohormones, represent an integral part of the plant signaling networks and therefore play multiple roles in controlling the growth, development and response to genetic, biotic and abiotic alterations (Rubio *et al.*, 2009; Santner *et al.*, 2009; Depuydt and Hardtke, 2011; Benkova, 2016). The initially discovered, classical phytohormones comprise gibberellins (GAs), cytokinins (CKs), auxins (Auxs),

abscisic acid (ABA) and ethylene (ET), which were amended by the more recently discovered hormones salicylic acid (SA), brassinosteroids (BRs), jasmonates (JAs) and strigolactones (SLs) (Kende and Zeevaart, 1997; Ross and O'Neill, 2001; Verma *et al.*, 2016). These phytohormones can act within the complex signaling networks that control various biological processes via antagonistic and/or synergistic actions. It has been reported that SA, JAs and ABA are involved in plant responses to multiple

stresses, whereas Auxs, CKs and SLs are involved in apical dominance and GAs, ABA and Auxs have been shown to control growth and cellular differentiation processes (Kende and Zeevaart, 1997; Ross and O'Neill, 2001; Rubio *et al.*, 2009; Santner *et al.*, 2009; Vegvari and Videki, 2014; Benkova, 2016).

In recent years several methods have been reported for the extraction and analysis of phytohormones (Koshiba, 2010; Ljung *et al.*, 2010; Fu *et al.*, 2011; Tarkowská *et al.*, 2014; Delatorre *et al.*, 2017; Novák *et al.*, 2017; Wang *et al.*, 2017; Šimura *et al.*, 2018). Contrary to the highly abundant primary and secondary metabolites, phytohormones are often only present in trace amounts in distinct plant tissues (Schafer *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, their comprehensive analysis requires specific extraction and enrichment procedures in order to increase the relative concentrations of the phytohormones of interest and to deplete other, possibly interfering, molecules (Liu *et al.*, 2007; Pan *et al.*, 2010).

Mass spectrometry (MS), mostly coupled to liquid chromatography (LC) and less frequently coupled to gas chromatography (GC), has in the last decade become the method of choice to detect and quantify phytohormones (Kojima *et al.*, 2009; Pan *et al.*, 2010; Flokova *et al.*, 2014; Lu *et al.*, 2015; Kasote *et al.*, 2016; Schafer *et al.*, 2016; Vallarino and Osorio, 2016; Cao *et al.*, 2017; Delatorre *et al.*, 2017; Wang *et al.*, 2017; Šimura *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, ultraperformance liquid chromatography (UPLC) has replaced the more commonly used LC systems for this work. UPLC relies on smaller (<2 μm) particles used for the packing of the column, offering higher chromatographic speed, sensitivity and resolution, compared with classical HPLC systems (Swartz, 2005; Denoroy *et al.*, 2013; Gosetti *et al.*, 2013).

Although multiple studies have been performed to comprehensively profile phytohormones (Kojima *et al.*, 2009; Pan *et al.*, 2010; Flokova *et al.*, 2014; Lu *et al.*, 2015; Kasote *et al.*, 2016; Schafer *et al.*, 2016; Vallarino and Osorio, 2016; Cao *et al.*, 2017; Delatorre *et al.*, 2017; Wang *et al.*, 2017; Šimura *et al.*, 2018), only a few studies have broadened their view on the systemic analysis of primary and secondary metabolites as well as phytohormones from the same sample (Schafer *et al.*, 2016; Cao *et al.*, 2017). By contrast, several comprehensive approaches using transcriptomic analysis were complemented by specific metabolic and phytohormone profiling. In these studies it was shown that complex molecular processes were activated in plants in response to water-deficit and osmotic stresses (Urano *et al.*, 2009; Harb *et al.*, 2010; Skirycz *et al.*, 2010; Urano *et al.*, 2017). Although these more comprehensive, 'omics'-based studies, in combination with phytohormone profiling, have provided valuable insights into stress responses, most of them have focused mainly on transcriptional changes,

with the broader metabolomics and proteomic profiles being neglected. As transcriptional levels are not necessarily correlated with protein levels or enzymatic activities (Liu *et al.*, 2016), the integration of metabolomics, lipidomic and proteomic analyses, together with the quantitative analyses of phytohormones from the same sample, will be essential for the molecular and mechanistic understanding of plant responses to stresses such as water deficit. An interesting step in this direction was, however, provided by a recently published proteogenomic approach studying the ABA response in *Arabidopsis* (Zhu *et al.*, 2017). This study combined RNA sequencing and proteomics and provided insight into the complexity of differential transcriptional initiation and alternative splicing in response to ABA treatment. Still, in order to better understand physiological processes such as plant growth, development and stress adaptation, it will likely be beneficial to collect even broader data sets and combine them with complex systems biology data analysis (Mast *et al.*, 2014). Accordingly, an ideal analytical method should provide the comprehensive extraction and systematic subfractionation of multiple compound classes from a single sample and their subsequent analysis using diverse MS-based profiling methods.

In the current study, an extraction method is described that is based on a previously developed method for the analysis of primary and secondary metabolites, lipids, starch, cell wall sugars and proteins (Gavalisco *et al.*, 2011; Salem *et al.*, 2016; Salem *et al.*, 2017). Here, this method was further improved and expanded towards the comprehensive analysis of phytohormones. The simple but substantial extension of the method relied on the use of acidified water for the induction of the liquid:liquid phase separation, enabling the complete purification of major plant hormones into the organic (methyl-*tert*-butyl-ether) phase. An aliquot of the extracted hormones was resuspended in methanol:water and separated by reversed-phase (RP) UPLC coupled to electrospray ionization (ESI) and a quadrupole/linear ion trap (QLIT) mass analyzer. The improved method, therefore, allowed for the quantification of the major phytohormone classes, polar and semi-polar metabolites, lipids, starch and proteins from a 50-mg aliquot of plant tissue. Control experiments demonstrated that despite the fact that certain phytohormones and phytohormone conjugates, particularly GAs and indole-3-acetic acid conjugates, are potentially degraded upon incubation on acidic conditions (Šimura *et al.*, 2018), such hydrolysis was not apparent during the extraction and quantification protocol reported here. The applicability of the method to address biological questions is demonstrated in a proof-of-concept experiment for the comprehensive, single-extract 'multi-omics' analysis of *Arabidopsis thaliana* leaf tissue from plants that were subjected to water-deficit stress.

RESULTS

Setting up an UPLC-MS/MS workflow for the analysis of phytohormones

Targeted LC-MS-based profiling of plant hormones using a quadrupole/linear ion trap (QLIT), triple-quadrupole (QqQ) mass analyzer, or a quadrupole high-resolution (qHR) mass analyzer, has been commonly shown to provide high sensitivity and broad specificity for the detection and quantification of these plant-specific metabolites (Koshiba, 2010; Ljung *et al.*, 2010; Pan *et al.*, 2010; Flokova *et al.*, 2014; Lu *et al.*, 2015; Schafer *et al.*, 2016; Cao *et al.*, 2017; Delatorre *et al.*, 2017; Wang *et al.*, 2017; Šimura *et al.*, 2018). Accordingly, similar to the previous studies, we established specific MS-MS/MS methods using a QLIT MS on authentic reference standards of the most relevant plant hormones (Figure S1). To verify the characteristics of every single hormone, a precursor ion and two fragment ions were determined by multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) of available phytohormone standards using direct infusion. Although the most abundant fragment ion of each precursor was selected for the quantification of phytohormones from plant tissues, the second fragment ion was used for the confirmation of the identity of the selected precursor.

The optimized MS-MS/MS methods, which contain all of the required parameters to analyze the individual hormones by MS are summarized in Table 1, whereas exemplary MS and MS/MS spectra of ABA, SA and GA₃ are presented in Figure S2.

Once the MRM methods for the analysis of the selected phytohormone classes were established (Table 1), we needed to establish a fast and sensitive LC method for the reproducible separation of the phytohormones prior to the MS-MS/MS analysis. The separation of metabolites on LC systems can be influenced by various parameters, including the chemical composition and the particle size of the column material, the column temperature employed, the pH and ion strength of the mobile phases, the LC flow rate and the slope of the LC gradient (Hayes *et al.*, 2014). In recent years, more LC columns with smaller particle sizes (<2 μm) have been developed (UPLC columns), which provide higher chromatographic resolution, leading to narrower peak widths and accelerated analysis times (Swartz, 2005; Denoroy *et al.*, 2013; Gosetti *et al.*, 2013). In the method described here, we compared several UPLC column chemistries in combination with different buffer systems and gradients. Based on our comparative testing, a high-strength silica (HSS) T3

Table 1 Multiple reaction monitoring transitions for phytohormones

Phytohormone	Scan mode	Q1 precursor ion(<i>m/z</i>)	Q3 product ions(<i>m/z</i>)	Retention time, RT (min)	Declustering potential, DP (V)	Entrance potential, EP(V)	Collision energy, CE (eV)	Collision cell exit potential, CXP(V)	Quantitation (<i>m/z</i>)
Abscisic acid (ABA)	neg.	263.04	152.9	4.13	-75	-10	-16	-23	152.9
		[M-H] ⁻	219	4.13	-75	-10	-20	-17	
Gibberellic acid (GA ₃)	neg.	345.09	142.9	1.87	-90	-10	-42	-21	142.9
		[M-H] ⁻	239	1.87	-90	-10	-22	-19	
Indole-3-butyric acid (IBA)	neg.	202.017	157.9	4.9	-80	-10	-20	-25	157.9
		[M-H] ⁻	115.7	4.9	-80	-10	-24	-17	
Indole-3-carboxylic acid (ICA)	neg.	160.001	115.9	2.22	-65	-10	-22	-17	115.9
		[M-H] ⁻	65.8	2.22	-65	-10	-66	-9	
Jasmonic acid (JA)	neg.	209.072	58.9	5.58	-70	-10	-26	-7	58.9
		[M-H] ⁻	96.8	5.58	-70	-10	-26	-15	
Salicylic acid (SA)	neg.	136.698	64.9	3.08	-20	-10	-42	-9	92.8
		[M-H] ⁻	92.8	3.08	-20	-10	-24	-13	
Jasmonoyl-L-isoleucine (JA-Ile)	neg.	322.18	129.8	7.7	-100	-10	-30	-19	129.8
		[M-H] ⁻	171.9	7.7	-100	-10	-24	-27	
<i>trans</i> -Zeatin (<i>tZ</i>)	pos	220.155	135.9	1.46	61	10	25	6	135.9
		[M+H] ⁺	202	1.46	61	10	19	12	
Indole-3-acetic acid (IAA)	pos	176.118	130	4.67	66	10	23	6	130
		[M+H] ⁺	77.1	4.67	66	10	69	2	
Brassinolide (BL)	pos	481.422	95	7.85	91	10	45	16	95
		[M+H] ⁺	71	7.85	91	10	47	12	
Gibberellin A ₄ (GA ₄)	pos	333.215	315.1	7.78	41	10	13	10	315.1
		[M+H] ⁺	269.2	7.78	41	10	27	8	
12-oxo-Phytodienoic acid (OPDA)	pos	293.26	275.2	8	66	10	19	8	275.2
		[M+H] ⁺	79	8	66	10	89	12	

reversed-phase (C₁₈) column and a 0.1% formic acid in water and 0.1% formic acid in methanol buffer system were finally selected. Using this combination of stationary and mobile phases, we were able to reduce the run time for the analysis of the major phytohormone classes to a total run time of 10 min, still maintaining excellent base-peak separation and narrow (3–9 sec), symmetrical peaks (Figures 1 and S3). As a consequence, the current phytohormone MS method allows the reproducible analysis of the major phytohormones from more than 70 samples within 12 h.

Improving a 'multi-omics' extraction method for the efficient partitioning of phytohormones into the organic phase

Several methods have been reported to use a single organic solvent, such as methanol, acetone, isopropanol, ethyl acetate or dichloromethane, mixtures of these solvents or immiscible solvents for the specific extraction of selected or broad-range extraction of multiple phytohormones (Koshiba, 2010; Ljung *et al.*, 2010; Pan *et al.*, 2010; Fu *et al.*, 2011; Muller and Munne-Bosch, 2011; Flokova

Figure 1. Analysis of plant hormones by UPLC-ESI-MS/MS analysis.

(a) UPLC-MS/MS chromatogram of standard mixture (0.75 ng) of phytohormones in negative-ionization mode.

(b) Absolute quantification of plant hormones in 14-day-old *Arabidopsis* seedlings. Plant hormones were extracted by the method described here and compared with a protocol published by Pan *et al.* (2010).

et al., 2014; Miret *et al.*, 2014; Lu *et al.*, 2015; Kasote *et al.*, 2016; Schafer *et al.*, 2016; Delatorre *et al.*, 2017; Wang *et al.*, 2017; Šimura *et al.*, 2018). The composition of the extraction solvent, extraction time and pH are among the factors that influence the efficiency but also the specificity of the extraction method. In particular, the use of two immiscible solvents, which leads to the complete or partial partitioning of specific compounds in one or the other of the two solvent phases, provides high compound recovery rates but also the removal of compounds that might interfere with the LC-MS analysis (Pan *et al.*, 2010). A previously published methyl-*tert*-butyl-ether (MTBE):methanol (MeOH) extraction method, which can be used for the simultaneous analysis of lipids, metabolites, proteins and other macromolecules from a single sample aliquot (Salem *et al.*, 2016), prompted us to test whether it can also be used for the simultaneous extraction and analysis of plant hormones. The liquid:liquid partitioning, which is based on an initial extraction step using a single-phase mixture of MTBE:MeOH (3:1, v:v) before phase separation is forced by the addition of H₂O:MeOH (3:1, v:v) (Salem *et al.*, 2016; Salem *et al.*, 2017), provided excellent recovery and clean-up for polar to semi-polar metabolites, which are preferentially partitioned into the polar phase (H₂O:MeOH phase). Accordingly, we postulated that the method could be extended to the extraction of most phytohormones, as they have similar chemical properties as the polar organic acids (Figure S1). Interestingly, based on initial recovery tests, we found that the previously published protocol did not lead to a complete partitioning of the phytohormones into either the polar (MeOH:H₂O) or the organic (MTBE:MeOH) phases. To obtain an improved partitioning, we modified the protocol by maintaining the homogenous mixture of MTBE:MeOH (3:1, v:v) for the initial extraction (Salem *et al.*, 2016), but induced the liquid:liquid phase separation by the addition of H₂O acidified with 0.1% (v/v) HCl. This simple modification forced all targeted phytohormones into the organic phase (MTBE:MeOH) and led to their complete recovery.

In a subsequent step, the modified MTBE extraction method was evaluated for its performance using *A. thaliana* ecotype Col-0 (hereafter referred to as *Arabidopsis*) plant tissue. Initial validation experiments were performed according to the guidance for analytical method validation issued by the European Medicines Agency (EMA, 2006) and the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA, 2013). Calibration curves were obtained by running six different concentrations (0.01–1000 ng ml⁻¹) of the authentic plant hormones based on the addition of an external standard. For this purpose, a solution containing a mixture of all hormones was used for the analysis. The standard calibration curves for the analyzed phytohormones were linear over the selected concentration range (Table S1). To validate the recovery of the modified MTBE

extraction method, we compared the extraction efficiencies against a commonly used extraction method dedicated to the analysis of phytohormones (Pan *et al.*, 2010). As can be seen from Figure 1(b), the efficiency of the MTBE method is at least equal to the results obtained with the dedicated phytohormone method. An overview of the modified extraction method and UPLC-MS-MS/MS analysis is shown in Figure S4.

To further strengthen the quantitative character of the method, we made use of isotope-labelled internal standards (ISs) for each hormone, which can compensate for losses or inefficiencies during sample extraction, concentration or UPLC-MS analysis (Figures S5–S7). These isotope-labeled ISs demonstrate similar extraction efficiencies and chromatographic behavior as the corresponding non-labeled compounds (Stokvis *et al.*, 2005). Nevertheless, we observed that deuterated ISs showed earlier RT (5–8 sec) on RP columns compared with their corresponding non-labeled phytohormone standards (Figures S5 and S6). A similar observation has been reported previously as the deuterium isotope effect, which is thought to be caused by the decreased lipophilicity of the molecule when hydrogen atoms are replaced by deuterium (Wang *et al.*, 2007).

Experimental set-up for the comprehensive 'omics' analysis of water deficit-stressed *Arabidopsis* leaves

To validate the modified MTBE extraction method for its applicability to a complex biological system, we designed a nested extraction workflow to study the water deficit-induced molecular changes of *Arabidopsis*. For this purpose, plants were grown under standard long-day conditions (16 h of light and 8 h of dark) for 1 month and then water-deficit stress was induced with 6 days of water deprivation. Subsequently, samples from control (watered) and stressed (non-watered) plants were profiled for changes in their phytohormone, photosynthetic pigment, lipid, primary and secondary metabolite, protein and starch composition (Figure 2).

Water deficit stress-induced molecular changes of phytohormones

The 6 days of water deprivation did not alter the macro-morphological phenotypes. Similarly, no significant differences in chlorophyll and carotenoid content were detected under water-deficit stress conditions (Figure S8a). By contrast, an accumulation of several phytohormones was detected in response to water-deficit stress. ABA accumulated significantly (sevenfold) after 6 days of water deprivation, whereas the concentrations of SA and 12-oxo-phytodienoic acid (OPDA) showed a significant twofold increase (Figure 3). The highest accumulation after water-deficit stress was observed for the two jasmonates JA and JA-Ile, which showed 14- and 11-fold increases, respectively (Figure 3). By contrast, no significant changes were

Figure 2. A schematic of the steps for extraction and analysis of lipids, metabolites, hormones, starch, proteins and cell wall material from plant tissues using a single aliquot.

detected in the levels of the main cytokinin zeatin and the two auxins indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) and indole-3-carboxylic acid (ICA) (Figure 3). Unfortunately, GA species were not detected in the leaf tissues analyzed, as their concentrations were under the limit of detection (LOD).

Water deficit stress-induced molecular changes in lipids and metabolites

Beyond the analysis of pigments and phytohormones, the extraction method allowed us to obtain relative quantification of the contents of more than 200 different lipid species, covering all major plant lipid classes (Table S2). To obtain an overview of the compositional variability of lipids before and after water-deficit stress, we performed a principal component analysis (PCA) using all lipid species identified. This PCA showed a clear separation between control and stressed plants along principal component 1 (PC1) (Figure 4a), suggesting that the lipid composition of *Arabidopsis* leaf was profoundly changed after the stress applied. Looking at these data more closely indicated that water-deficit stress led to a significant decrease in the content of monogalactosyldiacylglycerol (MGDG), whereas the

content of other chloroplast galactolipids such as digalactosyldiacylglycerol (DGDG) and sulfoquinovosyldiacylglycerol (SQDG) were unchanged following water-deficit stress (Figure 4b). By contrast to the increase in MGDG, the most abundant phospholipids, namely the phosphatidylcholines (PCs) and phosphatidylethanolamines (PEs), decreased significantly following water-deficit stress, whereas other phospholipids including the phosphatidylserines (PSs) and phosphatidylinositols (PIs) were, by and large, unaltered. Similar to the PS and PI species, several ceramides showed minor, mostly non-significant changes (Table S2). By contrast, triacylglycerides (TAGs), phosphatidylglycerols (PGs) and oxylipins increased significantly upon water deprivation (Figure 4b; Table S2). Besides the increase in TAGs, which represent the major pool of hydrophobic carbon storage molecules, a second major carbon storage pool, namely starch, also accumulated significantly upon water-deficit stress (Figure S8b).

To further explore the metabolic changes following water-deficit stress, the levels of primary and secondary metabolites were investigated using GC- and UPLC-MS, respectively (Tables S3 and S4). The PCA of the metabolite

Figure 3. Absolute quantification of hormone extracted from control and water-deficit stressed *Arabidopsis* leaves. Error bars indicate means \pm SEs for five biological replicates. Black asterisks indicate significant differences between control and stressed plants ($^*P < 0.05$, $^{**}P < 0.01$, $^{***}P < 0.001$, Student's *t*-test). FW, fresh weight.

profiles of control and stressed plants demonstrated that water-deficit stress allows for a clear separation from the control, reflecting changes in primary and secondary metabolism (Figure 5a,b). As for hormones and lipids, several primary and secondary metabolites accumulated upon water-deficit stress. Most prominent and consistent was the accumulation of several amino acids (Figure 6). Specifically, the levels of tryptophan, proline, lysine, histidine and

isoleucine, showed more than three-fold increase following the imposition of water-deficit stress (Figure 6). Metabolites involved in the TCA cycle, including fumarate, malate and succinate, also increased significantly in stressed plants (Table S3). Similarly, sugars, sugar alcohols and different organic acids increased significantly after water-deficit stress (Figure 7a), which was equally true for most of the stress-related secondary metabolites, including

Figure 4. Effects of water-deficit stress on lipid accumulation in rosette leaves of 36-day-old *Arabidopsis thaliana* plants.

(a) Principal component analysis (PCA) of the lipids identified by UPLC-MS analysis.

(b) Water-deficit stress induces significant changes in lipids.

Black asterisks indicate significant differences between control and stressed plants (* $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$, Student's *t*-test).

flavonoids, anthocyanins, glucosinolates and sinapates (Figure 7b).

Water deficit stress-induced molecular changes in global proteomic composition

Although the total leaf protein concentration did not change upon water-deficit treatment (Figure S8c), we assumed that there might be water deficit-induced differences in the cellular protein composition. To address this issue, we performed a comprehensive analysis of the leaf proteome using LC-MS/MS. The analysis of the proteins resulted in more than 3000 unambiguously identified proteins. Of the 3000 proteins identified, 602 distinct proteins changed significantly ($P < 0.05$) after water-deficit stress (Table S5). To gain insights into the biological functions of these proteins, gene ontology (GO) analyses were performed. From our proteomics data, biological processes that are involved in translation, glycolysis, photosynthesis and chloroplast organization were over-represented (Table S6). Among the 100 most abundantly increased proteins, biological processes associated with secondary metabolism, including the biosynthesis of JA (GO:0009695), cinnamate (GO:0009800) and flavonoids (GO:0009813), and the catabolism of Phe (GO:0006559) and Tyr (GO:0006572), were over-represented, as were abiotic and biotic-stress responses (Table S7). On the other hand, processes involved in ribosome biogenesis (GO:0042254), chlorophyll biosynthesis (GO:0015995) and translation (GO:0006412) were over-represented in the 100 proteins showing the largest decrease (Table S8).

As proteins involved in JA biosynthesis and responses were significantly enriched among the proteins increased under water-deficit stress conditions, we asked whether the proteins involved in phytohormone biosynthesis, catabolism, transport, perception and signaling also showed

changes. Consistent with the increased levels of JA and JA-Ile (Figure 3), several proteins in JA biosynthesis, including LOX2, AOS, AOCs and OPR3, were increased under water-deficit stress conditions (Table S9). In contrast to the situation observed for jasmonates, the increased levels of ABA (Figure 3) did not lead to a significant increase in the level of the biosynthetic protein BG1, a key β -glucosidase that catalyzes the hydrolysis of the ABA glucose ester (ABA-GE), leading to the formation of active ABA (Lee *et al.*, 2006) (Tables S10 and S11). Although a limited number of proteins were detected, some marker proteins in response to JA and SA, such as VSP1, VSP2 and PR2 (Ward *et al.*, 1991; Berger *et al.*, 1995), were also increased (Tables S9 and S11). Probably because IAA, CK and GA are mainly biosynthesized in young leaves and meristems, very few proteins associated with these phytohormones were identified (Tables S12–S14).

DISCUSSION

Optimization of hormone extraction, purification and quantitative analysis

The plant leaf, as well as all other plant tissues, represents a complex and challenging matrix for systems-wide molecular analysis after genetic, chemical or environmental perturbation. One of the essential molecular systems controlling the cellular response to changing stimuli consists of the intricate plant hormonal system, which consists of a diverse set of small molecules (Rubio *et al.*, 2009; Santner *et al.*, 2009; Depuydt and Hardtke, 2011; Benkova, 2016). Accordingly, the broad analysis of these essential regulatory compounds will, contextually, enable the determination of common and specific cellular responses that control complex transcriptional, proteomic and metabolomic regulatory networks, enabling physiological adaptation

Figure 5. Principal component analysis (PCA) of primary (a) and secondary (b) metabolites identified by GC-MS and UPLC-MS analyses, respectively.

Figure 6. Changes in the accumulation of amino acids and amino acid derivatives after water-deficit stress. Error bars indicate means \pm SEs for five biological replicates. Black asterisks indicate significant difference between control and stressed plants ($*P < 0.05$, $**P < 0.01$, Student's *t*-test).

Figure 7. Effects of water-deficit stress on primary and secondary metabolite accumulation in rosette leaves of 36-day-old *Arabidopsis thaliana* plants.

(a) Changes in the accumulation of sugars after water-deficit stress.

(b) Water-deficit stress induces significant changes in secondary metabolites.

Error bars indicate means \pm SEs for five biological replicates. Black asterisks indicate significant differences between control and stressed plants (* $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$, Student's *t*-test).

to changing growth conditions (Chiwocha *et al.*, 2003). The quantitative or semi-quantitative analysis of phytohormones has been established and indeed much improved in recent years (Liu *et al.*, 2007; Pan *et al.*, 2010; Flokova *et al.*, 2014; Lu *et al.*, 2015; Schafer *et al.*, 2016; Delatorre *et al.*, 2017; Wang *et al.*, 2017; Šimura *et al.*, 2018). Nevertheless, to understand and monitor the resulting molecular changes induced by different perturbations comprehensively, it is desirable to not only extract information on a few selected regulatory compounds, but also to obtain as much information as possible concerning the cellular biomolecules from as small sample as possible. The main

challenge for achieving this is in obtaining extracts of a complete metabolome, including polar metabolites from the central metabolism, as well as secondary metabolites, phytohormones and lipids, with the differing chemistries and dynamic ranges of these diverse molecules, from a single sample aliquot. Whereas central metabolites, such as sugars, and organic and amino acids, are present in the micromolar range, several of the signaling molecules, including some of the phytohormones, are present in nano- or even picomolar concentrations. Therefore, the ideal analytic method should provide efficiency within the extraction to cover as many metabolites as possible but

also display high selectivity, allowing for the quantification of low-abundance metabolites in the presence of background noise from the highly abundant metabolites.

To meet this challenge, we decided to improve our previously published analytical workflow, consisting of a liquid:liquid extraction method coupled to diverse UPLC-MS-based metabolomics and proteomic measurements (Salem *et al.*, 2016). Incorporating the phytohormone analysis into the initial fractionation and purification workflow (Salem *et al.*, 2016) not only required de-complexation and sample clean-up before the efficient phytohormone analysis, but also the complete partitioning of these diverse compounds into one of the two liquid:liquid fractions. Indeed, this is the crucial improvement offered by our current method, as opposed to the previously published methods. The introduction of acid rendered most hormones, which contain acid groups, to be charged and concentrated solely in the water phase, thus allowing for absolute quantification. For this purpose, our improved extraction method now includes an optimized buffer system, consisting of HCl-acidified water, for the complete partitioning of ABA, auxins, cytokinins, GAs, JAs and SA into a single phase (Figure 1a,b). Accordingly, reducing the pH allowed the phytohormones, which in most cases contain an acidic carboxyl group, to reach a neutral net charge and distribute mostly into the organic, MTBE, phase. Importantly, given that acids can potentially result in the hydrolysis of hormone conjugates, we carried out a control experiment in which the extract was incubated in acid for 30 min, and for 1 and 2 h, and the levels of the hormones were measured. As can be seen in Figures S9 and S10, there was little or no effect of lengthening the acid treatment of either authentic standards or plant extracts (with the exception of the slight yet significant decrease in SA content of plant extracts after 2 h), thus validating the general reliability of the method. We did, however, realize that GAs are present at the limit of detection of the method. As a result, for the sake of the biological comparison presented below, we measured GA in a different aliquot using an independent protocol specifically designed for GA detection (Figure S11). It is important to note that although the use of this independent protocol is required for *Arabidopsis* it is likely that the protocol developed here would suffice for other plant species, such as *Solanum lycopersicum* (tomato), for example, that contain higher levels of GA (Serrani *et al.*, 2007). The use of MTBE, as compared with dichloromethane, which has been used in several reports for hormone extraction (Pan *et al.*, 2010), offers a number of advantages. First, MTBE has a lower density and thus resides on the top of the polar phase after phase separation, thereby facilitating the collection of the hormones from the upper phase. Moreover, the boiling point of MTBE (55.2°C) is lower than that of other solvents used for hormone extraction, such as isopropanol (82.3°C), ethyl

acetate (77.1°C), methanol (64.7°C), chloroform (61.2°C) and acetone (56.3°C). This low boiling point allows for easier evaporation and, hence, decreases the loss of labile hormones during evaporation. Taken together, this method therefore maintains the advantages of the previously published MTBE extraction protocol, used for the comprehensive analysis of metabolites, lipids and proteins (Salem *et al.*, 2016), and additionally allows for the comprehensive profiling of most phytohormone classes (Figures 2 and S4). Interestingly, as a result of the partitioning of the phytohormones into the organic, MTBE, phase, we were able to omit further, expensive and time-consuming purification steps, such as solid phase extraction (SPE), while still allowing high compound selectivity and recovery (Tables S1–S4).

Application of the improved MTBE extraction method for the multi-omics analysis of lipids confirms previous data of water deficit-stress

To demonstrate the versatility of the extraction method described here for the broad system-wide analysis of metabolites, lipids, plant hormones and proteins, we decided to challenge *Arabidopsis* plants with a single water-deficit stress treatment for 6 days. Previously published data indicated that not only does the cellular lipid composition change during dehydration, to contribute to membrane stabilization, but also an absolute change in lipid class composition can be observed. So it was described that one of the most crucial dehydration responses leads to the absolute decrease in plastidic galactolipids, as compared with the concentration of cellular phospholipids (Torres-Franklin *et al.*, 2007). This massive decrease is mostly driven by the significant decrease of species from the MGDG class, which therefore also leads to a significant decrease in the intra-galactolipid ratio of MGDG:DGDG (Torres-Franklin *et al.*, 2007). Our results are in full accordance with these lipid-based water-deficit stress responses. Accordingly, the MGDG concentration is decreased by 20% compared with non-treated leaves, whereas the concentration of DGDG did not show significant changes (Figure 4; Table S2). The decrease in MGDG following water-deficit treatment is a common adaptation that has been reported in *Arabidopsis* (Gigon *et al.*, 2004; Tarazona *et al.*, 2015). As a result of the small head-group size, MGDG has a cone-shaped, non-lamellar hexagonal structure, whereas DGDG, with a larger head-group size, has a cylindrical-shaped lamellar structure (Webb and Green, 1991). Therefore, the proportion of MGDG and DGDG is important for the stability of the chloroplast membrane by maintaining the bilayer conformation that is necessary for membrane biological function (Dormann and Benning, 2002). As a consequence, the resulting decrease of MGDG:DGDG by 15% (Table S2) can participate in the stabilization of the lamellar bilayer structures during stress

(Gigon *et al.*, 2004; Gasulla *et al.*, 2013). MGDG of *Arabidopsis* contains mostly 34:6 molecular species, consisting of an 18:3 acyl group in the *sn*1 position and a 16:3 acyl group in the *sn*2 position, in agreement with the classification of *Arabidopsis* as a 16:3 plant (Heinz and Roughan, 1983; Browse *et al.*, 1986). The decrease of MGDG 34:6, which was also the predominant MGDG species in our lipid data, therefore clearly explains the significant reduction of the whole MGDG class upon water-deficit treatment (Table S2).

Analysis of non-polar lipids revealed, as previously reported (Gasulla *et al.*, 2013; Tarazona *et al.*, 2015), that TAGs accumulated significantly (by 36%) following water-deficit stress (Figure 4; Table S2). Phospholipids, particularly PCs and PEs, decreased significantly following water-deficit stress (by 15 and 21%, respectively), whereas PGs increased significantly by 46% (Figure 4; Table S2). The general decrease in the most abundant phospholipids, namely the PCs and PEs, was consistent with published data (Gasulla *et al.*, 2013). Indeed, the decrease in membrane lipids is one of the first lipid phenotypes observed in plants following water-deficit stress (Gigon *et al.*, 2004). One of the most striking changes in lipid composition following water-deficit treatment was the massive increase in oxylipins (Table S2), which corresponds to the trends described in previously published data (Tarazona *et al.*, 2015). Other lipid classes, including the plastidic SQDG and the cellular membrane lipids PSs and ceramides by and large remained unchanged (Table S2).

Analysis of primary metabolites, phytohormones and proteins reveals known and previously undescribed molecular changes after water-deficit stress

The combination of -omics approaches, such as transcriptomics and metabolomics, has previously been performed to understand complex molecular mechanisms underlying plant responses to osmotic stresses. Accordingly, phytohormones have very well-known adaptive stress responses to unfavorable conditions (Rubio *et al.*, 2009; Santner *et al.*, 2009; Depuydt and Hardtke, 2011; Benkova, 2016). ABA, SA, JA, amino acids, such as Pro, Trp and Lys, and sugars, such as glucose, fructose and raffinose, accumulated significantly under stress conditions (Figures 6 and 7), which is consistent with previous profiling of metabolites and phytohormones in response to dehydration (Urano *et al.*, 2009; Harb *et al.*, 2010; Skirycz *et al.*, 2010; Urano *et al.*, 2017). According to gene expression changes, it has been suggested that the upregulation of *NCED3* and *AAO3*, which encode ABA biosynthetic enzymes, is essential for ABA accumulation in response to dehydration (Urano *et al.*, 2017). Unfortunately, these key proteins were not detected in our LC-MS/MS analysis, whereas BG1 was significantly increased at the protein level (Table S10). Given that dehydration activates the promoter of *BG1* and its ABA-GE hydrolyzing activity

(Lee *et al.*, 2006), our result therefore suggests that the conversion of inactive ABA-GE to active ABA in leaves plays an important role under water-deficit stress conditions, whereas the role of *de novo* ABA biosynthesis via the *NCED3* and *AAO3* proteins remains to be established. Moreover, consistent with increases of JA, JA-Ile and their precursor OPDA (Figure 3), the transcript level of their biosynthetic enzymes *LOX2* and *OPR3* have been described to increase in response to dehydration (Urano *et al.*, 2017). These results seem to match nicely with the observed decrease of MGDG (Figure 4b; Table S2), as MGDG, especially the most abundant MGDG species 34:6, can be processed by lipases to produce the polyunsaturated fatty acids linolenic acid (18:3) and hexadecatrienoic acid (16:3). Oxygenation of these fatty acids by LOXs is then the initial step of JA biosynthesis (Acosta and Farmer, 2010). Our results therefore seem to suggest that the main proportion of JAs might be generated by the degradation of MGDG and the synthesis of OPDA and dnOPDA (Figures 3 and 4).

Whereas ABA has been well documented as a crucial phytohormone in the stomatal regulation and induction of genes in water-deficit stress resistance, the biological roles of JA under these stress conditions are still under debate. So it has been shown that methyl jasmonate (MeJA) elicits stomatal closure as well as ABA in several species (Gehring *et al.*, 1997; Suhita *et al.*, 2004; Munemasa *et al.*, 2007). Moreover, a recent study has demonstrated that OPDA, the precursor of JA, is increased more distinctly by water deficit than by wounding, and has an additive effect on the stomatal closing of ABA (Savchenko *et al.*, 2014), implying that MeJA and OPDA have roles in preventing water loss during water-deficit stress. Intriguingly, beyond the significant accumulation of OPDA, we detected significant increases in MeJA after water deficit (Table S4); however, in contrast to ABA, the accumulation of JA was reported to be faint or transient during dehydration (Creelman and Mullet, 1995; Urano *et al.*, 2017). As can be seen in Figure S11, despite the trend of increasing under water-deficit stress, the levels of GA4 are not significantly different from those in the control. Furthermore, JA-response mutants, such as *coi1* and *jin1*, have been shown to be more resistant to moderate water-deficit stress in terms of plant biomass (Harb *et al.*, 2010), suggesting negative roles of JA signaling on growth under stress conditions. Further studies will be required to elucidate how JA, its derivatives JA-Ile and MeJA, and also its precursors OPDA and MGDG are involved in stress responses under water-limited conditions.

Similar to the observed changes in the phytohormone profiles, several primary metabolites, such as Pro, as well as secondary metabolites, including flavonols and anthocyanins, have been shown to be accumulated in response to water deficit (Nakabayashi *et al.*, 2014a). Consistently, our UPLC-MS data demonstrated increased levels of flavonoids, anthocyanins, glucosinolates and sinapates in

leaves under water-deficit stress conditions (Figure 7b). Given that *Arabidopsis* plants overproducing antioxidant flavonoids displayed increased water-deficit stress tolerance, as a result of reduced levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in leaves and decreased water loss (Nakabayashi *et al.*, 2014b), increased concentrations of secondary metabolites might be important to prevent excess ROS accumulation. By contrast, microscopic studies coupled with the quantification of flavonols by mass spectrometry have revealed that the levels of flavonols, such as kaempferol and quercetin, in guard cells are negatively and positively associated with ROS levels in guard cells and stomatal aperture, respectively (Watkins *et al.*, 2014; Watkins *et al.*, 2017), indicating that an increase of flavonols in guard cells may lead to increased water loss via stomata. As flavonols in guard cells are thought to be regulated by ethylene (Watkins *et al.*, 2014; Gago *et al.*, 2017; Watkins *et al.*, 2017), further analyses of phytohormones and secondary metabolites in mesophyll and guard cells might unveil the roles of secondary metabolites under water-deficit stress conditions.

In summary, in the current study we have reported a modified multi-omics protocol allowing the accurate quantification of a range of phytohormones alongside polar metabolites, lipids, starch and proteins. Control experiments indicated that the use of acidified water did not influence the quantification of the phytohormones under the experimental conditions used, despite previous studies suggesting that this may present a problem (Šimura *et al.*, 2018). We furthermore used this protocol to provide a deeper characterization of water-stress deficit, allowing the determination of changes in specific galactolipids concomitant with the accumulation of a number of fatty-acid derivatives and jasmonates alongside the classical ABA-defined responses to water-deficit stress. We believe that this protocol will prove useful in providing comprehensive information concerning a wide range of hormone-regulated processes.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Reagents and chemicals

Authentic plant hormones (abscisic acid, ABA; gibberellin acid, GA₃; gibberellin A₄, GA₄; indole-3-acetic acid, IAA; jasmonic acid, JA; jasmonoyl-L-isoleucine, JA-Ile; 12-oxo-phytodienoic acid, OPDA; salicylic acid, SA; *trans*-Zeatin, tZ) and internal standards [²H₆](+)*cis,trans*-abscisic acid, [²H₂]gibberellin A₄, indol-3-acetic-2,2-[²H₅] acid, [²H₂](±)-jasmonic acid, [²H₃]N-[(-)-jasmonoyl]-leucine, [²H₅]*cis*-12-oxo-phytodienoic acid, [²H₄]salicylic acid and [²H₅]*trans*-Zeatin (HPLC grade, purity >99%) were purchased from OlChemIm (<https://www.olchemim.cz>). All the standard hormones were stored according to the recommendations of the supplier. LC-grade solvents were obtained from Biosolve Chemicals (<http://www.biosolve-chemicals.eu>). All other chemicals were of analytical reagent grade. Hydrochloric acid (HCl) was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (<https://www.sigmaaldrich.com>).

Preparation of solutions and extraction solvents

The individual standards were dissolved in LC-grade methanol at a stock of 1 mg ml⁻¹ and stored protected from light at -20°C until use. Working solutions of authentic hormones (ranging from 1000 to 0.01 ng ml⁻¹) and internal standards (50 ng ml⁻¹) were prepared by serial dilution of the stock solution in methanol:water (50:50, v:v) prior to analysis. The extraction solvent mixture contained methyl-*tert*-butyl-ether:methanol (MTBE:MeOH, 3:1, v:v) and was prepared together with isotope-labelled internal standards (ISs) at a concentration of 50 ng ml⁻¹; the extraction solvent was kept at -20°C (Salem *et al.*, 2016; Salem *et al.*, 2017). The solvent for phase separation during hormone extraction, containing water acidified with 0.1% HCl, was prepared and kept at 4°C. The solvent for phase separation during metabolite extraction, containing water:methanol (3:1, v:v), was prepared and kept at 4°C.

Plant growth conditions

Seeds of the model plant *A. thaliana* of the ecotype Col-0 were sown on pots containing artificial standard soil: 70% (v/v) white peat; 20% (v/v) vermiculite; 10% (v/v) sand; 1 kg m⁻³ Triabon®, 100 g m⁻³ iron chelate, pH 5.5–6.0; supplemented with 1 g L⁻¹ Osmocote Start; Einheitserde Gs90 (Gebrüder Patzer, <https://www.einheitserde.de>). For synchronous germination, pots were transferred to a cold (4°C) and dark growth chamber for 3 days before they were grown in a long-day (LD) growth chamber maintained with a 16-h light/8-h dark cycle. The average light intensity was maintained at 150 μmol m⁻² sec⁻² and the day/night temperature and relative humidity were maintained at 20/16°C and 60/75%, respectively. For water-deficit stress treatment, plants were irrigated on a regular basis for 1 month, after which time watering was stopped for 6 days. Samples (rosette leaves from five biological replicates) were harvested at the middle of the day from control untreated and water-deficit treated 36-day-old plants and snap frozen in liquid nitrogen. The plant material was ground into a homogeneous and fine powder and then aliquoted (50 mg) into 2-ml safe-lock microcentrifuge tubes. The samples were stored at -80°C until further sample extraction.

Extraction of plant hormones

Plant samples (five biological replicates per treatment) were extracted with 1 ml of pre-cooled (-20°C) extraction MTBE/MeOH solvent. After mixing by vortexing, samples were kept on an orbital shaker for 30 min at 4°C followed by a 15-min sonication step in an ice-cooled bath-type sonicator. A volume of 0.5 ml of acidified water (0.1% HCl) was added and the samples were again thoroughly vortexed for 1 min. After that, the samples were kept on an orbital shaker for an additional 30 min at 4°C. The samples were centrifuged at 10 000 g for 10 min at 4°C. A fixed volume (0.8 ml) of upper supernatant (MTBE phase) was transferred to a fresh 1.5-ml microcentrifuge tube and dried down using a Speed-Vac concentrator at 25°C room temperature (RT) (concentration to dryness take up to 1 h at 30°C). The dried pellets were resuspended in 100 μl of water:methanol (50:50) solution and the resuspended samples were immediately subjected to UPLC-ESI-MS/MS hormonal analysis.

Chromatographic conditions for UPLC analysis

A UPLC system (e.g. Waters Acquity UPLC system; Waters, <https://www.waters.com>), consisting of an auto-injector, column oven, two binary pumps, degasser and low-volume mixer, was used. Analytical UPLC separation was achieved on a reversed-phase

(RP) C18-column. A high-strength silica (HSS) T3 column (100 mm × 2.1 mm, containing 1.8- μ m diameter particles; Waters) fitted with a 2.1 × 5-mm guard column (ACQUITY UPLC HSS T3 VanGuard Pre-column, 100 Å, 1.8 μ m; Waters) was used for this method. A UPLC separation method performed using a binary solvent system consists of water containing 0.1% (v/v) formic acid (solvent A) and methanol containing 0.1% (v/v) formic acid (solvent B). The gradient parameters for RP-UPLC separation in negative ionization mode were as follows: 62% eluent A for 6.5 min; 45% eluent B from 6.5 to 7.0 min; 10% eluent A from 7.0 to 7.1 min, held at 0% eluent A from 7.1 to 8.1 min and returned to initial conditions by 8.1 min. From 8.1 to 10.0 min the column was re-equilibrated and conditioned to 62% eluent A. The analysis in the positive mode was performed using the same gradient but starting with 80% eluent A instead of 62% eluent A. The column temperature was set at 40°C. The flow rate was 0.4 ml min⁻¹. The autosampler temperature was set at 10°C. The injection volume was 7.5 μ l.

Optimization of MS/MS conditions

MS/MS analysis was achieved using a suitable quadrupole/linear ion trap (QLIT) mass analyzer (e.g. 4000 QTRAP; AB Sciex Germany GmbH, <https://sciex.com>) with a multiple-reaction monitoring (MRM) scan type equipped with an electrospray ionization (ESI) source (e.g. Turbo V™ Ion Source; AB Sciex) and attached to the UPLC system. ANALYST 1.6.2 (AB Sciex) was used for instrument control, data acquisition, processing and analysis. MRM transitions for authentic hormones and internal standards were obtained by direct infusion of each compound (100 ng ml⁻¹ in 50% methanol/water containing 0.1% formic acid) into the mass spectrometer using a 0.5-ml syringe (SGE Analytical Science, <http://www.sge.com>) through a syringe pump (Fusion 100T; Chemyx, Inc., <https://www.chemyx.com>) at 10 μ l min⁻¹. The operating parameters for MS/MS analysis were as follows: ion polarity, positive or negative; ion source, turbo spray; capillary ion spray voltage, 5.5 kV or -4.5 kV for positive or negative ion polarity, respectively; probe tip position, 3 mm; source temperature, 500°C; gas, nitrogen; curtain gas, 25 psi; nebulizing gas (GS1) and focusing gas (GS2), 40 psi; interface heater, on; collision-activated dissociation gas pressure, medium.

Calibration curves and validation of the method performance

Quantification was performed using external calibration standards. Standard mixtures containing all phytohormones were prepared from the stock solution of individual hormones by dilution in 50:50 (v:v) methanol:water to six different concentrations (1000, 100, 10, 1, 0.1 and 0.01 ng ml⁻¹). Calibration curves were performed by plotting the peak areas of hormones against their concentrations and the curves were fitted by least-squares linear regression using a 1/x weighting factor. The regression equation and correlation coefficient (R^2) were obtained from ANALYST 1.6.2 (AB Sciex). The final optimized method was evaluated for the performance of the LC/MS/MS analysis. Validation experiments were performed according to the guidance for analytical method validation issued by the European Medicines Agency (EMA, 2006) and the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA, 2013). The limit of detection (LOD) was defined as a signal (S) to background noise (N) ratio of S/N > 3, whereas the limit of quantification (LOQ) was defined by S/N > 10. Additionally, the precision of the method was evaluated through repeatability experiments (intra-day and inter-day precision) (Gustavo González and Ángeles Herrador, 2007).

Extraction of hormones, lipids, metabolites, proteins and starch from a single sample

Homogenized plant samples (five biological replicates of 50 mg per condition) were extracted by incubation with 1 ml of pre-cooled (-20°C) MTBE:MeOH (3:1, v:v) mixture, spiked with 0.05 μ g ml⁻¹ of internal standards of hormones, metabolites and lipids (Salem *et al.*, 2016; Salem *et al.*, 2017). The extracts were incubated for 30 min on an orbital shaker at 4°C before sonicating them for 15 min on an ice-cooled sonication bath. The samples were centrifuged for 10 min at 10 000 *g* at 4°C. The supernatant was transferred to two new microcentrifuge 2-ml tubes, each with 0.5 ml of the supernatant: one for hormone extraction and the other for lipids and metabolites extraction. The precipitated pellet was washed with 0.5 ml of methanol and used for the successive extraction of proteins and starch (Salem *et al.*, 2016). To the first supernatant (tubes for hormone extraction), a volume of 0.5 ml of acidified water (0.1% HCl) was added and the samples were again thoroughly vortexed for 1 min. After that, the samples were kept on an orbital shaker for an additional 30 min at 4°C. The samples were centrifuged at a speed of 10 000 *g* for 10 min at 4°C. The upper supernatant (MTBE phase) was collected and put in a 1.5-ml microcentrifuge tube, dried down using a SpeedVac concentrator at RT (samples take up to 1 h at 30°C). The dried pellets were resuspended in 50 μ l water:methanol (50:50) solution and the resuspended samples were immediately subjected to UPLC-ESI-MS/MS hormonal analysis.

To the second supernatant (tubes for lipid and metabolite extraction), a volume 0.5 ml of water:methanol (3:1, v:v) was added and the samples were quickly vortexed and finally centrifuged for 10 min at 10 000 *g* at 4°C. An aliquot (250 μ l) from the upper phase was collected for UPLC/MS lipid analysis, whereas two other aliquots (200 and 250 μ l) of the lower phase were collected for GC/MS and UPLC/MS analysis of primary and secondary metabolites, respectively. All of the aliquots collected were dried in a speed-vacuum concentrator (Salem *et al.*, 2016; Salem *et al.*, 2017).

The dried lipid samples were resuspended in 0.1 ml of UPLC-grade acetonitrile:isopropanol (70:30) mixture, followed by vortexing and 10 min of incubation in an ultrasonication bath. Samples were centrifuged for 5 min at 10 000 *g*. A 2- μ l portion of the sample was injected, separated on an Acquity UPLC system using an RP C8 column and analyzed by MS (Hummel *et al.*, 2011). The samples were measured in positive and negative ionization mode. The mass spectra were acquired using an Orbitrap high-resolution mass spectrometer: Fourier-transform mass spectrometer (FT-MS) coupled with a linear ion trap (LIT) Orbitrap XL (ThermoFisher Scientific, <https://www.thermofisher.com>). The first dried residues from the polar phase were derivatized with *N*-trimethylsilyl-*N*-methyl trifluoroacetamide (MSTFA) (Lisec *et al.*, 2006). The derivatized sample was injected onto the GC column (DB-35MS, 30 mm × 0.32 mm internal diameter, 0.25- μ m film thickness; Agilent, <https://www.agilent.com>) in splitless mode. The GC/MS system consisted of an Agilent 7686 series autosampler (Agilent) coupled to an Agilent 6890 gas chromatograph coupled to a LECO Pegasus 2 time-of-flight mass spectrometer (LECO, <https://www.leco.com>). The second dried samples from the polar phase were resuspended in 0.1 ml of UPLC-grade water:methanol (50:50) mixture, followed by vortexing and 10 min of incubation in an ultrasonication bath. Samples were centrifuged for 5 min at 10 000 *g* at 4°C. A 2- μ l portion of the sample was injected, separated on an Acquity UPLC system using an RP C18 column and analyzed by MS (Giavalisco *et al.*, 2011). The samples were measured in

positive and negative ionization modes. The mass spectra were acquired using an Orbitrap-type high-resolution mass spectrometer (Exactive; ThermoFisher Scientific).

Extraction and analysis of pigments, proteins and starch

For the measurement of chlorophyll *a* and *b* as well as total carotenoids, an aliquot of 100 μ l was taken from the non-polar fraction (the MTBE layer). The samples were diluted with methanol to 1 ml and the absorption UV-VIS spectra were measured as described in our protocol (Salem *et al.*, 2016). For protein extraction, after metabolite extraction the washed pellet was resuspended in 0.2 ml of protein buffer consisting of 6 M urea, 2 M thiourea, 15 mM dithiothreitol (DTT), 2% 3-[(3-cholamidopropyl)dimethylammonio]-1-propanesulfonate (CHAPS), and protease and phosphatase inhibitors. The samples were incubated on an orbital shaker (100 rpm) at room temperature for 30 min. Protein concentrations were determined after centrifugation and 50 μ g of protein extract was digested in-solution using a Trypsin/Lys-C mixture (MS grade; Promega, <https://www.promega.com>) according to the instruction manual. The digested samples were de-salted, concentrated and finally analyzed by LC-MS/MS using a Q ExactivePlus high-resolution MS connected to an EASY-nLC 1000 system (ThermoFisher Scientific) (Salem *et al.*, 2016; Salem *et al.*, 2017).

Starch was gelatinized from the washed pellets after protein extraction by heating at 100°C for 1.5 h. Starch was enzymatically digested with α -amylglucosidase and α -amylase mixture, according to the manufacturer's instructions. The digested samples (40 μ l) were mixed with 0.16 ml of glucose assay mix, consisting of 100 mM 4-(2-hydroxyethyl)-1-piperazineethanesulfonic acid (HEPES), pH 7.5, hexokinase (6 U ml⁻¹), 4 mM MgCl₂, 0.5 mM adenosine triphosphate (ATP) and 1 mM nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD⁺). After monitoring the initial absorption at 340 nm, glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (0.25 U) was added to each sample before recording the absorption again. Starch concentration was determined based on a calibration curve of a standard glucose (Salem *et al.*, 2016; Salem *et al.*, 2017).

Stand-alone GA measurements

About 200 mg of fresh-frozen materials were used to extract and purify the GA, as described by Plackett *et al.* (2012), with the following minor modifications: material was extracted with 80% acetonitrile containing 1% acetic acid (10 ml) for 1 h at 4°C. After centrifugation at 3000 *g* for 20 min and collection of the supernatant, the residue was re-extracted by mixing with the same solvent, followed by centrifugation. The acetonitrile was evaporated and the residue dissolved in 2 ml of water containing 1% acetic acid, followed by sonication for few minutes. The aqueous residue was loaded onto an OASIS HLB cartridge (60 mg, 3 cc; Waters) and prewashed/equilibrated consecutively with 3 ml of acetonitrile, methanol and 1% aqueous acetic acid. After washing with 1% aqueous acetic acid (3 ml), GAs were eluted with 80% acetonitrile containing 1% acetic acid (2 \times 3 ml). The dried eluate was dissolved in 700 μ l of water containing 1% acetic acid and passed through a SepPak silica cartridge (100 mg; Waters), prewashed with MeOH (2 \times 700 μ l) and 0.1 M HCl (700 μ l). The extract was loaded onto an equilibrated MCX column, eluted by acetonitrile and evaporated. The residue was dissolved in 700 μ l of water containing 1% acetic acid. The aqueous residue was loaded onto a Wash WAX solid-phase column after prewashing with MeOH and then 0.1 M NaOH, and then equilibrated by water. The column was then washed by MeOH and eluted by 80% acetonitrile containing 1% acetic acid, and the eluted fraction was evaporated and dissolved in 30 μ l of water containing 1% acetic acid. The levels of

GAs were quantified with the UPLC system coupled to a Triple Quad MS, as described above.

Analysis of phytohormone stability during extraction

Arabidopsis plants of ecotype Columbia-0 (Col-0) were cultivated for 21 days in a glasshouse with a 16-h light/8-h dark cycle at 20°C and 60% relative humidity. The entire rosettes of four independent biological replicates were harvested in individual 2-ml tubes and immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen. Samples were aliquoted in 15-ml tubes and extracted with the methodology described above, with the distinction that twice the quantity of material and extraction buffers were used and the entire MTBE fraction was used for the phytohormone HCl 0.1% extraction. Three aliquots of 500 μ l from the MTBE phase of each biological replicate were then kept for 30, 60 and 120 min on the orbital shaker. Further steps for drying, re-suspension and analysis were performed as described in above. The stability of the measured phytohormones in the extraction conditions was evaluated by comparing each time point against the 30-min control via a Student's *t*-test. The same procedure was repeated for extracting and analyzing mixtures of the phytohormones standards. Instead of the plant material, three aliquots of 100 μ l were taken from two independent 1 mM mixtures containing all standards.

Data processing and statistical analysis

The obtained LC/MS raw chromatograms from metabolites and lipids were manually inspected using XCALIBUR™ 2.2 (ThermoFisher Scientific), followed by automated spectra processing using PROGENESIS QI FOR METABOLOMICS 2.3 (Nonlinear Dynamics, <http://www.nonlinear.com>). Peaks from raw chromatograms were first determined and then aligned by their parent masses, chemical noise was subtracted and a final alignment file of all chromatograms was obtained, containing information about *m/z*, retention time and the intensities of each annotated peak. The peaks were assigned using an in-house Arabidopsis lipid and metabolite database, according to retention time and parent masses. The data matrix obtained was then further processed for normalization and statistical analyses. Proteomic data were analyzed using PROGENESIS QI FOR PROTEOMICS 3 (Nonlinear Dynamics). Proteins were identified from PROGENESIS-generated .mgf files using MASCOT 2.5 (Matrix Science Ltd, <http://www.matrixscience.com>), trypsin as the digestion enzyme, carbamidomethyl as a fixed modification and oxidation as a variable modification, allowing for one missed cleavage. Peptide tolerance was set to 10 ppm and fragment mass tolerance was set to 0.1 Da. Protein identifications were filtered with a false-discovery rate of better than 1%, at least two peptides, one unique peptide and a score of 50. Search results were exported from MASCOT in .xml format and imported back into PROGENESIS QI for further protein analysis. For GC-MS data analysis, chromatograms were exported from LECO® CHROMATOF-GC 3.34 to R (<https://www.r-project.org>). Peak detection, retention time alignment and library matching were performed using the TARGET SEARCH R package (Cuadros-Inostroza *et al.*, 2009). Data obtained from LC- or GC-MS analysis were normalized by fresh weight, followed by using internal standard normalization. Data presentation and experimental details are provided in Appendixes S1 and S2 following the current recommendations for reporting metabolite data (Fernie *et al.*, 2011). All statistical analyses were performed using the algorithms embedded within Microsoft EXCEL. The significance of differences was tested for each metabolite by Student's *t*-test ($P < 0.05$). Bar graphs were plotted using either EXCEL or SIGMA PLOT 12.5 (<http://www.sigmaplot.co.uk>). Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed in METABOANALYST 3.0 (Xia *et al.*, 2015),

following \log_2 -transformation and Pareto scaling (the centered mean is divided by the square-root of the SD of each variable). Heat-map representation was performed using MULTIEXPERIMENT VIEWER 4.9.0 (Saeed *et al.*, 2003).

Statistical and gene ontology analysis of proteins

Significantly increased or decreased proteins were detected by an empirical Bayes method (Kammers *et al.*, 2015), with minor modifications. Among 3329 annotated proteins, redundant proteins annotated in two or more loci and those encoded by splice variants of a locus were excluded. The proteins harboring missing values in five biological replicates were also excluded, resulting in 3255 distinct proteins. By using open-source software (Kammers *et al.*, 2015), estimated \log_2 fold changes corresponding to the effect size and moderated *P* values corresponding to the moderated *t*-statistic were calculated. For GO analysis, over- or under-represented biological processes were searched on the PANTHER Classification System (<http://pantherdb.org>) (Mi *et al.*, 2017) using Fisher's exact test with false-discovery rate (FDR) multiple test correction.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

MAS, ARF and PG conceived and designed the research. MAS, TY, LPS, SA and KB performed the experiments. MAS, TY, LPS and SA analyzed the data and performed the statistical analysis. MAS, ARF and PG wrote the article. All the authors read and approved the article after critical revision.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declared no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

All the data generated and used in this study are available upon request or as supporting information for this article.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional Supporting Information may be found in the online version of this article.

Figure S1. Structures of plant hormones analyzed/

Figure S2. MS and MS/MS spectra of reference hormones.

Figure S3. UPLC-MS/MS chromatogram of standard mixture (0.75 ng ng) of phytohormones in negative (A) and positive (B) ionization modes. UPLC running conditions were described in Experimental procedures.

Figure S4. Schematic overview of the liquid:liquid extraction and UPLC-MS-MS/MS analysis of hormones from plant tissues.

Figure S5. UPLC-MS/MS chromatograms of *Arabidopsis thaliana* leaf extract spiked with labelled internal standards of SA. XIC, extracted ion chromatogram; TIC, total ion chromatogram.

Figure S6. UPLC-MS/MS chromatograms of *Arabidopsis thaliana* leaf extract spiked with labelled internal standards of ABA. XIC, extracted ion chromatogram; TIC, total ion chromatogram.

Figure S7. UPLC-MS/MS chromatograms of *Arabidopsis thaliana* leaf extract spiked with labelled internal standards of IAA. XIC, extracted ion chromatogram; TIC, total ion chromatogram.

Figure S8. Absolute levels of photosynthetic pigments (A), starch (B) and total protein (C) after water-deficit stress.

Figure S9. Box plot depicting LC-MS peak area for each measured phytohormone in *Arabidopsis* leaf material per time of exposure to MTBE/HCl 0.1% extraction.

Figure S10. Box plot depicting LC-MS peak area for each measured phytohormone in 100 μ L of a standard mixture per time of exposure to MTBE/HCl 0.1% extraction.

Figure S11. Box plot depicting LC-MS peak area of GA4 for control and water deficit.

Table S1. Analytical performance data of the MRM transitions selected for the quantification of phytohormones.

Table S2. Lipid data analyzed using UPLC/FT-MS from control and water-deficit treatments.

Table S3. Metabolite data from control and water-deficit treatment analyzed using GC-TOF MS.

Table S4. UPLC/FT-MS data of metabolites from control and water-deficit treatments.

Table S5. Significantly changed proteins under water-deficit stress conditions detected by nLC/MS/MS analysis.

Table S6. Over- or under-represented gene ontology (GO) processes among the total identified proteins.

Table S7. Over- or under-represented gene ontology (GO) processes among the top 100 proteins increased under water-deficit stress conditions.

Table S8. Over- or under-represented gene ontology (GO) processes among the bottom 100 proteins decreased under water-deficit stress conditions.

Table S9. Quantitative changes of proteins in JA and JA-Ile metabolism, transport, perception and signaling.

Table S10. Quantitative changes of proteins in ABA metabolism, transport, perception and signaling.

Table S11. Quantitative changes of proteins in SA metabolism, transport, perception and signaling.

Table S12. Quantitative changes of proteins in IAA metabolism, transport, perception and signaling.

Table S13. Quantitative changes of proteins in CK metabolism, transport, perception and signaling.

Table S14. Quantitative changes of proteins in GA metabolism, transport, perception and signaling.

Appendix S1. Metabolite data report for the compounds analyzed by LC/MS in this study.

Appendix S2. Metabolite data report for the compounds analyzed by GC/MS in this study.

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